

HIPPARCOS

On the generation of pseudo-random deviates for simulation experiments

by L Lindegren, Lund Observatory (1980-10-20)

Pseudo-random deviates, i.e. numbers generated in a completely deterministic and repeatable way, but having statistical properties almost indistinguishable from those of "true" random numbers, are usually employed in numerical simulations to represent observational errors or noise. Formulae for generation of such numbers are summarized below. It is proposed to use a highly portable and statistically satisfactory algorithm by Schrage (1979) as a basis.

1. Uniform distribution, $U]0,1[$

Real numbers $r \in U]0,1[$, i.e. having a uniform distribution in the interval $0 < r < 1$, are most conveniently generated by the congruence method. A sequence of positive integers $IX(i)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots$, are obtained from the recursion

$$IX(i+1) = a \cdot IX(i) + b \pmod{P}, \quad (1)$$

where a , b , P are suitable integers and the sequence is initialized with some value $IX(0)$ in the range $0 < IX(0) < P$. The real numbers $r(i) = IX(i)/P$ then have the desired properties.

We propose to use the particular generator

$$a = 7^5 = 16807, \quad b = 0, \quad P = 2^{31} - 1 = 2147483647 \quad (2)$$

described by Schrage (1979). Direct implementation of (1) requires integer operations with an accuracy of at least 46 bits (to represent $a \cdot P$), but Schrage shows how the recursion can be implemented either if integer representation with ≥ 32 bits is at hand, or using double precision arithmetic.

It is suggested that the generator is initialized with $IX(0)$ of the order of P , e.g.

$$IX(0) = 10^9. \quad (3)$$

Initialization $IX(0) = 1$ gives the abnormally small first random fraction $r(1) = 0.000007826\dots$

Below it is assumed that a real function $RAND(IX)$ is available, generating numbers $r \in U]0,1[$.

2. Normal distribution $N(0,1)$

The set of normal (gaussian) random deviates with zero mean and unit variance is denoted $N(0,1)$. Pseudo-random deviates $g \in N(0,1)$ may be obtained from uniformly distributed pseudo-random numbers $r \in U]0,1[$ by several different methods and transformations (see Abramowitz and Stegun, 1970). We propose the use of the following transformation which is statistically "exact", although rather slow.

Let r_1 and r_2 be two independent random numbers from $U]0,1[$. Two independent random normal deviates from $N(0,1)$ are then obtained by the transformation

$$\begin{aligned} g_1 &= (-2 \ln r_1)^{\frac{1}{2}} \cos(2\pi r_2), \\ g_2 &= (-2 \ln r_1)^{\frac{1}{2}} \sin(2\pi r_2). \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

This follows from the fact that $v = g_1^2 + g_2^2$ is χ^2 -distributed with two degrees of freedom, $\Pr[v > x] = \exp(-x/2)$.

A possible Fortran implementation of the function GAUSS(IX) generating pseudo-random normal deviates is the following:

```
REAL FUNCTION GAUSS(IX, IQ)
  IF (IQ .GT. 0) GO TO 10
  IQ = -IQ
  GAUSS = HOLD
  RETURN
10 R1 = RAND(IX)
  R2 = RAND(IX)*6.2831853
  A = SQRT(-2.*ALOG(R1))
  GAUSS = A*COS(R2)
  HOLD = A*SIN(R2)
  IQ = -IQ
  RETURN
```

(5)

The integer IQ is used to keep track of odd/even number of calls. IQ must be initialized as a positive integer.

3. Quasi-normal distribution with an excess of large deviations

Empirically, observational errors are usually found to exhibit a certain excess of large deviations from the mean, as compared with the normal distributions, even when all "obviously erroneous" observations have been removed. It may be desirable to incorporate this feature in the error generator. A simple model would be to assume that a small fraction (q) of the errors belong to a population with w (> 1) times the standard deviation of the remaining errors. Thus it may be found that 1 % of the errors have a standard deviation 3 times that of the remaining 99 % ($q = 0.01$, $w = 3$). This may be implemented as follows:

```
REAL FUNCTION QGAUS(IX, IQ, Q, W)
  QGAUS = GAUSS(IX, IQ)
  IF (Q .LE. 0.) RETURN
  IF (RAND(IX) .LT. Q) QGAUS = QGAUS*W
  RETURN
```

(6)

4. Poisson distribution

Simulation of photoelectron counts requires an algorithm for generating a non-negative integer (n) following the Poisson distribution with given mean value ($a \geq 0$):

$$\Pr[n = m] = \frac{a^m}{m!} \exp(-a), \quad m = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (7)$$

One method (Carnahan, Luther, Wilkes, Applied Numerical Methods, Example 8.2) is to generate a sequence of numbers $r_0, r_1, r_2, \dots \in U]0,1[$. Then the lowest

value of n for which the product $r_0 r_1 r_2 \dots r_n$ is less than or equal to $\exp(-a)$, is a random variable having the Poisson distribution with mean a . Another method is to generate only one number $r \in]0,1[$, and then accumulate the series

$$p_n = \left(1 + \frac{a^1}{1!} + \frac{a^2}{2!} + \dots + \frac{a^n}{n!}\right) \exp(-a) \quad (8)$$

until $p_n > r$. Then n is Poisson distributed with mean a . The preferred method depends on the relative slowness of the RAND function and the accumulation of terms in (8).

In either case the number of operations required to generate n increases linearly with n (or a); in addition, there will be numerical difficulties with large a (e.g. underflow when computing the exponential function). Thus a different algorithm is needed for large a .

Since the Poisson distribution is asymptotically normal as $a \rightarrow \infty$ (with mean a and variance a), we can use the generator for $N(0,1)$ to obtain an approximation to the Poisson distribution. The most naive transformation is simply to put

$$\begin{aligned} N &= \text{INT}(A + \text{SQRT}(A) * \text{GAUSS}(IX) + 0.5) \\ \text{IF } (N \text{ .LT. } 0) \text{ } N &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

A much better approximation (even for quite small values of a , say 10 or less) is obtained with the slight modification

$$\begin{aligned} G &= \text{GAUSS}(IX) \\ N &= \text{INT}(A + \text{SQRT}(A) * G + 0.17 * G ** 2 + 0.33) \\ \text{IF } (N \text{ .LT. } 0) \text{ } N &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

A provisional algorithm, using (8) for $a < 10$ and (10) for $a \geq 10$ is the following:

```

INTEGER FUNCTION NPOIS(A, IX, IQ)
  IF (A .GE. 10.) GO TO 20
  NPOIS = 0
  TERM = 1.
  SUM = 1.
  C = RAND(IX) * EXP(A)
10 IF (SUM .GT. C) RETURN
  NPOIS = NPOIS + 1
  TERM = TERM * A / FLOAT(NPOIS)
  SUM = SUM + TERM
  GO TO 10
20 G = GAUSS(IX, IQ)
  NPOIS = INT(A + SQRT(A) * G + 0.17 * G ** 2 + 0.33)
  IF (NPOIS .LT. 0) NPOIS = 0
  RETURN

```

(11)

References:

- Abramowitz and Stegun, Handbook of Mathematical Functions (Section 26.8),
Dover, New York (1970)
- Schrage, L., A More Portable Fortran Random Number Generator,
ACM Transactions on Mathematical Software, Vol 5, p 132 (1979)

TEST OF GAUSS Nov-80

